

ABC Salt

Advanced Biomass
Catalytic Conversion

NEWS

Issue 1

November 2018

Biofuels advancements begin

Foreword

In front of you is the first ABC-Salt newsletter. The project, sponsored by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 program, started in April this year and aims to develop technology at small lab scale for the conversion of biomass and particularly waste agricultural residues to middle distillates. Or in simpler words: from straw to a fuel for a Boeing 787.

This is not an easy task, it involves breaking down the complex molecular structure of biomass containing significant amounts of bound oxygen into an oxygen free, low molecular weight product. Catalysts play a major role here and have the function to effectively depolymerize the biomass structure and to remove the bound oxygen. We aim to develop both novel processing media, catalysts and integrated technology to make the process

as efficient as possible. The project is not about the scale up of an existing concept to pilot plant or even a semi-commercial unit but aims to convert novel ideas in the field into a workable small scale lab unit.

But the project is not all about technology. Our product is an advanced biofuel. Already the word biofuels worries people, creating images of deforestation and food issues. As such, we are also very keen on getting to know the response of the general public on biofuels from agricultural residues in general and ours in particular. In case of barriers, we would like to prioritize them and develop strategies to mitigate them.

We are also particularly keen on communicating our results to the outside world for instance using newsletters (in front of you) and our public web site. Please visit us at www.abc-salt.eu.

The first project meetings have been held already in Groningen (The Netherlands) and Stockholm (Sweden). Set-ups have been developed and initial testing with various biomass feeds has just started. Further progress will be presented in the next newsletters!

With best regards,

Erik Heeres - Project coordinator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement number 764089

PROJECT OVERVIEW

ABC-Salt is a new four year project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

It will validate a novel route to produce sustainable liquid biofuels at laboratory scale. Nine European partners from academia, industry and research organisations are collaborating to create new technologies with the potential to reduce global dependence on fossil fuels and support the EU towards achieving a low-carbon economy.

ABC-Salt is an acronym for Advanced Biomass Catalytic Conversion to Middle Distillates in Molten Salts and aims to solve a number of technical challenges in biofuels production. ABC-Salt will receive nearly four million Euros from Horizon 2020, after launching at the University of Groningen in April 2018.

Eight inter-related work packages have been developed to tackle the challenge of liquefaction and the subsequent catalytic hydro-pyrolysis of biomass in a molten salt environment, followed by the catalytic hydro-deoxygenation of the vapour phase using sustainable catalysts to obtain a hydrocarbon product suitable for use as a middle distillate biofuel. ABC-Salt will then operate an integrated lab scale reactor over 100 hours to provide lab-scale validation of the whole process, brining this technology to readiness level 4.

The project includes technical aspects, such as substrate flexibility, biomass liquefaction and hydro-pyrolysis in molten salts, as well as socio and techno-economic viability studies to ensure the future deployment of technologies is suitable for integration, considering substrate availability, supply chains, future end users and the overall economic sustainability of the process.

The holistic approach of this project considers the full value chain and includes a communications, promotion and dissemination element to ensure outcomes are effectively communicated.

A number of ABC-Salt Summer Schools and open workshops will also take place across Europe over

the next four years to maximise the impact of the project and ensure the implementation of new technologies is effective.

ABC-Salt aims to have a positive effect upon the biomass, biofuel and transport industries, developing sustainable new technologies that will reduce dependence on unsustainable fossil fuels and support progress towards the EU's achievement of a low-carbon economy by 2050.

Enquiries can be directed towards the project coordinator Erik J Heeres (h.j.heeres@rug.nl) at the University of Groningen (RUG). Further information can also be found on the project's new website at www.abc-salt.eu and followers can keep up to date via social media on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

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New to Biofuels? Here is a brief glossary to help bring you up to speed:

Bioenergy—any renewable energy produced by living organisms, such as plants and bacteria

Biofuel—a source of energy made from living matter. ABC-Salt focuses on using agricultural residues, which means there is no competition for land between food and fuel production. All the biomass used comes from leftovers, ensuring the energy produced in the form of biofuels is sustainable, renewable and capable of integration into Europe's existing economic infrastructure.

Biomass—biomass, sometimes referred to as feedstocks, is any organic matter used to make biofuel.

Fossil Fuel—an unsustainable natural fuel such as coal or gas made from the remains of animals buried thousands of years ago. The world is now dependent on fossil fuels for energy, but their use releases dangerous levels of CO₂ and sources are running out. A sustainable, renewable alternative, such as biofuel, is now needed.

PROJECT PARTNERS

ABC-Salt has nine European partners from academia, industry and research organisations working together over a four year period to develop and validate a novel route to produce sustainable liquid biofuels at laboratory scale.

The European Bioenergy Research institute (EBRI) is part of Aston University's School

of Engineering and has world-leading academic and research teams working on bioenergy research and technology. Aston University's technical research activities is delivered by Daniel Nowakowski, an expert in analytical pyrolysis, thermochemical and physical properties of biomass and biochars, and hydrothermal liquefaction. Aston University also leads the communications activities of ABC-Salt, overseen by Tony Bridgwater.

ABC-Salt's project coordinator is The **University of**

Groningen (RUG). Founded in 1614, it's one of the oldest and largest universities in the Netherlands. Erik J Heeres' research group is part of the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences and a member of the ENTEg institute. It is active in the development of novel catalytic chemistry and reactor concepts for catalytic processes with a strong emphasis on the conversion of lignocellulosic biomass to energy, biofuels and bio-based performance chemicals. The facilities' staff have diverse backgrounds, ranging from catalytic reaction engineering, heterogeneous catalysis and micro reactor technology. Advanced analytical tools for characterisation of complex bioliquids have also been developed.

The Biomass Technology Group BV (BTG) is a private company of

consultants, researchers and engineers specialised in sustainable energy production from biomass and waste. BTG's expertise covers a broad variety of thermal bioenergy conversion technologies, including pyrolysis, hydro-heating, gasification, supercritical gasification, torrefaction, combustion, liquefaction and carbonisation. They are experienced and involved in European bioenergy research, demonstrating and research and development programmes, particularly related to biomass pyrolysis, oil hydrogenation and gasification. Robbie Venderbosch is an expert in thermal biomass conversion technologies and leads BTG's contribution to ABC-Salt.

Aymin has 30 years' experience improving businesses' operational and financial performance. Offering a range of consultancy and advisory services, covering procurement and supply chain, operational efficiency, innovation grant funding and management, Aymin are supporting the University of Groningen with project management activities.

Partners involved in technical research activities have also welcomed Early Career Researchers to contribute to the activities of ABC-Salt.

For more information about project partners, visit www.abc-salt.eu

RISE is the Swedish Research Institute, created with the merge of Inventionia, SP Technical Research institute of Sweden and Swedish ICT, with a long history of high quality research. In collaboration with industry, academia and the public sector, RISE ensures the business community's competitiveness and contributes to a sustainable society. RISE offers unique expertise and approximately 100 test beds and demonstration facilities, instrumental in future proofing technologies, products and services.

PROJECT PARTNERS

The Thermochemical Conversion of Biomass (TCCB) research group, led by Frederik Ronsse formed in 2008 at **Ghent University**. Research is centered on the development and optimization of thermochemical conversion technologies to create renewable fuels, chemicals and

energy from biomass. Research on thermochemical conversion technologies is devoted to pyrolysis (fast, catalytic and hydrolysis) for the production of liquid biofuels and chemical intermediates, slow pyrolysis for the production of biochar and torrefaction as a biomass pretreatment operation. Hydrothermal conversion technologies, gasification and post-conversion treatment of bio-oil, including upgrading and fractionation are also of interest. Biotechnology for a sustainable economy plays a key role in the study of production of biochar out of agricultural and biorefinery residues.

research area at DLR -ETT

The Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU) is

a research oriented university educating mainly MSc and PhD candidates. The Faculty of Science and Technology includes the research group for renewable energy technology, which spans activities such as biogas, solar energy and molten salt technology. It operates a dedicated laboratory for molten salt research and their experience in this area is well documented in peer reviewed publications, projects sponsored by the Research Council of Norway and its successful PhD candidates. Heidi S. Nygård leads NMBU's contribution to ABC-Salt. Her PhD studies at NMBU focused on the conversion of biomass liquid in molten salts and provided valuable insights that contributed towards the development of the ABC-Salt project. Her expertise extends to CO₂ capture in molten salts, with focus on the conversion of biomass to liquids.

DLR is the national aeronautics and space research centre of Germany. Its extensive research and development work in aeronautics, space, energy, transport and security is integrated into national and international cooperative ventures.

The Institute of Engineering Thermodynamics (DLR -TT) and its research efforts from 175 staff, are focused on efficient energy conversion and storage with low environmental impact, and on the improvement and acceleration of the use of renewable energy sources. The scientific spectrum includes electrochemical, thermochemical and thermal energy technologies covering the full range of materials, development, and system integration. Ralph Uwe-Dietric leads the Alternative Fuels

Sapienza University of Rome was

established in 1303 and is the largest University

in Italy. The Inter-University Centre for Research in Environmental Psychology (CIRPA), founded in 2005, aims to promote and develop the field of Environmental Psychology, by networking into one consortium all of the main Italian Universities interested in psychological research. Sapienza University of Rome's contribution investigates the impact of ABC-Salts technologies to contribute to a comprehensive socio-economic assessment of the viability of the new, renewable technologies under development. CIRPA's activities are led by Marino Bonaiuto, Director of CIRPA, whose interests in environmental psychology focus on how environmental features affect people and how people's behaviour affects the environment.

PROJECT WORK PACKAGES

Ethics (WP1)

This work package is led by project coordinators University of Groningen and ensures that the ABC-Salt project activities fully adhere to ethics requirements, including identifying and mitigating or eliminating any risks of possible harm to the environment

Techno-economic Evaluation (WP2)

ABC-Salt will develop a process to generate liquid fuels from biomass in an efficient and economical way. Led by DLR, the aims of this work package are to ensure the technology developed during ABC-Salt is technologically, economically, socially and environmentally relevant. This work package will consider the techno-economic, socio-economic and environmental evaluation, together with critical steps taken, as well as the overall socio-economic and acceptance study.

Primary Liquefaction (WP3)

Led by NMBU, the targeted objective of this work package will be to select the feedstock supply and the molten salts. Feedstocks will be selected to represent typical, low cost surplus supplies, readily available in Europe, while molten salt or salt mixtures will be chosen on the basis of chemical and physical properties.

Above: NMBU's Heidi S. Nygård at work

Hydro-pyrolysis in molten salts (WP4)

The fundamentals of hydro-pyrolysis of biomass in molten salts will be investigated, deriving reaction mechanisms to reveal the best conditions for carrying out molten salt hydro-pyrolysis, with the liquid product yield and quality as key performance indicators. The main objective is to identify suitable process conditions for hydro-pyrolysis.

Hydro De-Oxygenation (WP5)

Led by BTG the refining of oils produced from biomass by cracking in molten salts baths will be studied to optimise the bio-liquid as feed to produce middle distillates.

Demonstration of Integrated Concept (WP6)

On the basis of the results of work packages 3 to 6, an integrated lab scale reactor will be built to demonstrate the overall process to transform the selected feeds into middle distillates biofuels. Expected scale is around 100g/h.

Communication, Dissemination, Outreach Activities and Exploitation (WP7)

Led by Aston University with the involvement of all partners, this work package aims to maximise the impact of the ABC-Salt project, by a well-thought series of dissemination, exploitation and outreach activities.

Project Management (WP8)

ABC-Salt's project management work package is led by the University of Groningen, supported and administered by Ayming. This work package oversees all coordinative aspects.

For work package contact information,
see page 10

WORKSHOPS AND SUMMER SCHOOLS

As part of ABC-Salt's Dissemination and Communication activities, a series of Summer Schools and Workshops will take place across Europe during the project timeline until 2022.

These events present a unique opportunity to network with biofuels experts from across Europe, discover state-of-the-art technologies and cutting edge processes, develop connections for business and career development, as well as contribute and feedback to shape the future of biofuels and bioenergy research. All of which is essential to keeping the EU on track to meet its climate change goals and reduce overall dependence on unsustainable fossil fuels.

Summer Schools and workshops are open to members of public and private organisations, industry and academia, all parts of the bioenergy supply chain, as well as Early Career Researchers and colleagues from related European and international projects.

This first ABC-Salt summer school will focus on **Biomass Liquefaction in Molten Salts**. It is scheduled for August 2019 and will be held at the European Bioenergy Research Institute at Aston University in the United Kingdom, and is a joint activity with NMBU Norwegian University of Life Science.

Above: NMBU's Heidi S. Nygård. Sign up to ABC-Salt's first Summer School at Aston University, UK in August 2019 and meet project pioneers NMBU's Heidi S. Nygård and EBRI's Tony Bridgwater

All ABC-Salt Summer Schools are free to attend, funded by the project. At the first summer school in August 2019, thirty places will be available to the public on a first come, first served basis.

Light refreshments will be provided. Travel and accommodation is not included and will be at delegates own arrangement. Travel advice will be available on the ABC-Salt website in early 2019.

Registration will be opening in early 2019 online at www.abc-salt.eu.

Scheduled Date	Topic	Location
Summer School 1 12 –14 August 2019	Biomass Processing in Molten Salts Registration Available January 2019!	Aston University, UK
Workshop 1 2019 (TBC)	Mid-Term Project Update and the Social Setting for Advanced Biomass Catalysis Technologies	Rome—TBC
Summer School 2 2020 (TBC)	Biofuels from Lignocellulosic Biomass using Molten Salts Technology	Germany- TBC
Workshop 2 (TBC)	Final Project Findings	TBC

For more international biofuels events, visit www.abc-salt.eu/events

Molten Salt Discussion Group

Professor Espen Olsen (NMBU) presented the ABC-Salt project at the Molten Salt Discussion Group (MSDG) summer research meeting (24 — 26 July 2018, Downing College, Cambridge). MSDG has been actively involved in the field of high temperature molten salts and ionic liquids for over five decades. The Group provides a network of experienced scientists to offer professional advice to other members and it actively encourages scientists working in the field of molten salts, whether high temperature or low. Two meetings are held each year, one Summer meeting and one Christmas meeting, usually with around 30-40 attendants. The next meeting will be held in London on 17 December 2018.

The focus of the presentation at the Summer meeting was the selection of suitable molten salts for liquefaction of biomass. In the first months of the project period, NMBU has focused on a screening of potential low melting mixtures by going through scientific publications, books and patents. Furthermore, a systematic review of phase diagram databases has been carried out to search for less known mixtures. The salt mixtures with sufficiently low melting points have been studied further with regards to transport properties (e.g. viscosity, vapor pressure), and potential side reactions such as hydrolysis have been modelled. Several salts show potential for biomass liquefaction, and preliminary experimental liquefaction tests are currently being performed by the partners RUG and UGent.

Around 30 participants attended the MSDG Summer meeting 2018. The general feedback from the molten salt community was positive. Several researchers came with valuable suggestions for potential molten salt systems that will be pursued further in the ABC-Salt project.

Heidi S. Nygård

New Project Website

ABC-Salt has a brand new project website at www.abc-salt.eu, which was designed and developed by Aston University and launched in summer 2018.

The site contains core project and contact information. It will act as a gateway to the knowledge, developments and technological advancements expected throughout the lifetime of the ABC-Salt project. It will connect with document repositories, signpost towards relevant publication and be the centre of the ABC-Salt activities.

www.abc-salt.eu

Connect with ABC-Salt

ABC-Salt is now on social media!

Follow us on Twitter
@H2020 ABC SALT

Find us on LinkedIn: ABC-Salt

Email your project communications enquiries to
abc-salt@aston.ac.uk

Above: Catalytic research at the European Bioenergy Research Institute, Aston University, UK

ABC-SALT UPDATES

RISE

In October 2018, ABC-Salt project partners from across Europe met at RISE facilities in Stockholm, Sweden, marking six months since project launch, where they discussed progress and made important decision about the future of biofuels research. Key meetings were

held about all work packages, and partners had the rare opportunity to discuss their collaborative work

with each other in person. Two days' of meetings culminated in tours of RISE facilities.

It was also Emma Richet from Ayming's last meeting, as she leaves the project to move on to a new role. Her colleague Sophie Ablott takes over supporting the University of Groningen (RUG) with the project management work packages.

The next ABC-Salt project meeting is scheduled for early March 2019 in Rome.

Clockwise from top left: ABC-Salt project partners group photo; NMBU's Heidi S. Nygård presents on Molten Salt Screening; partners present from across the project; RISE's Maria Sedin presents on Lignin, CIRPA's Marino Bonaiuto engages with discussions alongside partners from Aston University and NMBU.

For more project information, visit www.abc-salt.eu

INTERNATIONAL BIOFUELS EVENTS

ABC-Salt was represented by Aston University at the Fuel and Energy Research Forum's [12th ECCRIA European Conference on Fuels and Energy Research and its Applications](#). It was

attended by researchers in industry and academia and took place on the 5th-7th September 2018 in Cardiff, UK. Visitors were able to pick up a flyer with details of the project and its website.

BRISK²

BIOFUELS RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

**Biofuels Research Infrastructure for
Sharing Knowledge**

New Summer School dates coming soon!

Next call for Transnational Access closes -
April 2019

Register your interest and find out more at

www.brisk2.eu or email brisk2@aston.ac.uk

AMBITION

**Advanced Biofuel Production with Energy
System Integration**

International workshop coming to the UK in
2019!

Register your interest and find out more at

www.ambition-research.eu

Biofuels and Bioenergy for Expanding a New Horizon

December 3-5, 2018 - Valencia, Spain

ICNP 2018

December 7-9, 2018 - Kerala, India

Horizon Scan Webinar for Technologies Related to Algae Cultivation—Pilots4U

December 10, 2018 - Online

C1net Conference 4 - Chemicals from C1 Gas

January 20-23, 2019 - Nottingham, United Kingdom

Lignofuels 2019

February 13-14, 2019 - Oslo, Norway

International Biomass Conference and Expo

March 18-20, 2019 - Savannah, Georgia

World Bio Markets 2019

April 1, 2019 - Amsterdam, Netherlands

4th Green and Sustainable Chemistry Conference

May 5-8, 2019 - Dresden, Germany

BEE 2019—2nd International Symposium on Bioenergy and Environment

May 9-12, 2019 - Taijin, China

EUBCE 2019

May 27—30, 2019 - Lisbon, Portugal

International Conference on Biofuels and Bioenergy

September 23-25, 2019 - Barcelona, Spain

**Visit www.abc-salt.eu/events for more
international bioenergy events.**

Feature your event in this newsletter.

Email: abc-salt@aston.ac.uk

KEY CONTACTS

General Enquiries: sablott@ayming.com

Project Co-ordinator

Erik H. J. Heeres
h.j.heeres@rug.nl

Project Management (WP8)

Sophie Ablott
sablott@ayming.com

Work Package 1 & 5

Robbie Venderbosch
venderbosch@btgworld.com

Sapienza University of Rome

Marino Bonaiuto
marino.bonaiuto@uniroma1.it

Work Package 2 & 6

Jos Winkelman
j.g.m.winkelman@rug.nl

DLR

Ralph-Uwe Dietrich
ralph-uwe.dietrich@dlr.de

Work Package 3

Heidi Nygard
heidi.nygard@nmbu.no

RISE Innventia

Maria Sedin
maria.sedin@ri.se

Work Package 4

Frederik Ronsse
frederik.ronsse@ugent.be

Senior Scientific Advisor

Wolter Prins
wolter.prins@ugent.be

Work Package 7 & Newsletter Editor

Pippa Try
p.try@aston.ac.uk

This newsletter is published annually and contributions are welcomed. Please send your articles and events listings to: **abc-salt@aston.ac.uk**. Include high resolution photos and an author profile. All submissions will be vetted and may be edited for quality before publication.